

Mapping the Data Galaxy at CZU

This document summarises the results of mapping research data management at CZU and serves as a basis for unifying rules, strengthening support, and further development in this field.

At the turn of April and May 2025, an online survey was conducted among researchers working at CZU faculties and the IEC. The questionnaire consisted of 58 questions and was completed by 227 respondents.

The mapping focused on the entire data lifecycle – from planning, through collection, processing and analysis, to preservation and potential sharing. The aim was to provide a clear description of everyday practice, the tools and repositories used, the level of available support, and the main barriers faced by researchers.

Comprehensive Report

Dataset

Key Findings

Local Data Storage

52 % of researchers do not create any meta-data, even though its contribution to science is essential. While 91% store data on multiple devices, they often choose insufficiently secure storage – such as portable media or personal computers. 22% do not create versions of their data, thereby exposing themselves to the risk of loss or theft.

Institutional Repositories

74 % of researchers would welcome a university repository. They wish to preserve their data securely and over the long term. Due to the lack of infrastructure, they currently resort to makeshift solutions.

Rules for Sharing

Data are shared mainly when strictly necessary. A systematic approach is lacking. Uncertainty regarding the handling of sensitive information prevents wider sharing – resulting in unused data that could otherwise be further applied.

Guidelines and Support

As many as 85% of researchers call for unified procedures, guidance, and support from the university. Without clearly defined rules for data management, they often have to improvise.

Data Quality and Security

30 % of researchers prefer to work with their own data, mainly due to concerns about the quality of external data and limited awareness of available repositories. The quality assurance and security of collected data are often insufficient. Advanced methods such as anonymisation or encryption are applied only rarely.

81% of researchers have no rules for data management or are unaware of them. Coordination at the institutional level is missing.

85% call for unified guidelines, support, and training.

Researchers prefer online support – information on websites, training, videos, and consultations.

Only 6% of researchers create Data Management Plans; this remains an exceptional practice rather than a standardised scientific procedure.

67% of researchers combine various methods of verifying the quality of collected data.

Plan

11% do not carry out any quality control during data collection.

39% of researchers apply no specific security measures during the data collection process.

Methods of data security during collection

Restricted access to data (authorised persons)	103
No specific measures taken	89
Data are stored only on secure storage systems	71
Anonymization/Pseudonymization during collection	13
Other	7
Data are encrypted immediately	7

Numer of responses

- 40 % of researchers do not protect their data during collection – often because they do not consider them sensitive
- 45 % restrict access to authorised persons
- 31 % use secure repositories
- 6 % anonymise data already at the point of collection
- 3 % use encryption

Collect

52% of researchers do not create metadata.

Of those who do, 61% use no standardised formats.

22% of researchers do not create versions of their data.

91% of researchers store data on multiple devices, which indicates a positive trend in terms of backup. However, the chosen storage locations are not always secure.

Analyse

Process

Share

Preserve

The main barriers to sharing include limited knowledge of procedures, concerns about data misuse, and the absence of central guidelines. This results in fragmented approaches and improvised solutions.

Only 10% of researchers use more secure tools (e.g. CESNET services).

59% of researchers have experience with data sharing – both as providers and as recipients.

89% of researchers share their active data.

In contrast, the rate of sharing inactive data drops significantly – by as much as one third. Sharing is often driven by immediate need rather than by an open science strategy.

- 69% of researchers archive inactive data on portable media
- 54% use personal computers for archiving
- 65% use university computers for archiving
- Only 8% store data in specialised repositories

Final data storage after the end of active work - not all categories are included

Researchers predominantly keep data locally, as a central university repository is lacking.

74% of researchers want a university repository.

Main reasons include:

- security (51%)
- long-term preservation (45%)
- technical support (38%)
- efficient data handling within the institution (35%)

Preserve

Preserve

Every second researcher stores data only on a local device without backup.

The Datanaut Embarks on a Data Mission!

The Datanaut is setting out on a journey across the galaxy of research data. At each stop, it explores the key areas that need to be strengthened in order to make robust data management a standard practice of research at CZU.

How to Support Data Management at CZU?

Sound data management begins with understanding its importance. The university should provide flexible training that introduces all the essential principles of data management – from the FAIR principles, through metadata and security, to ethics and law, always with regard to disciplinary specificities. The purpose of a Data Management Plan is to make researchers' work easier, not to burden them with unnecessary administration.

Whom to Turn to When Help is Needed?

The DMCC and the network of faculty-based data stewards form the basic support structure. This needs to be further strengthened – both professionally and in terms of capacity. The role of data stewards will be key, directly supporting individual researchers and research teams. In this way, it will be possible to build a functioning ecosystem that responds to individual needs while promoting robust data management.

Where Can I Store Data Safely?

CZU should develop and expand its own repository for secure and long-term data storage. At the same time, it should encourage the use of trusted disciplinary repositories in line with established standards.

How to Anchor Data Management in the University Culture?

Researchers need clear rules. A necessary university directive should establish unified standards while allowing faculties to adapt them to disciplinary requirements. Attention should also be given to security, interoperability, and ethical as well as legal aspects. A crucial component is the development of a data platform for secure storage.

Will Administrative Support Be Available?

Researchers need tools that make their work easier – contract templates, informed consent forms, and practical guidance. These materials will reduce administrative burden and enhance the quality of research at CZU.

Why Does This Matter?

High-quality data management enhances research quality and strengthens trust, openness, and accountability. It is the foundation of excellent science and the key to success in an environment where the principles of open science are gaining increasing prominence.

A small step for data. A giant leap for CZU.